

1 **Analysis of Hop Acids and Their Oxidized Derivatives and Iso- α -acids in**
2 **Beer by Capillary Electrophoresis–Electrospray Ionization Mass**
3 **Spectrometry**

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16

17 **Abstract**

18 This study investigates the applicability of on-line coupling of capillary electrophoresis with
19 electrospray ionization tandem mass spectrometry (CZE-ESI-MS) for the separation and
20 characterization of α and β -acids and oxidized hop acids from crude extracts of different hop
21 varieties. CZE-ESI-MS with negative-ion electrospray ionization proved to be a suitable
22 technique for the determination of these types of natural compounds and their oxidized
23 derivatives. The CZE parameters (pH, concentration, and buffer type) and ESI-MS parameters
24 (nature and flow rate of the sheath liquid, nebulizer pressure, drying gas flow rate,
25 temperature, and compound stability) were optimized. The optimized method provides the
26 potential for a fast qualitative determination of hop acids and their oxidation compounds. The
27 method was also applied to the determination of iso- α -acids in beer.

28

29 **KEYWORDS:** Acetone hop extract; hop acids; iso- α -acids; capillary zone electrophoresis;
30 mass spectrometry

31

32 INTRODUCTION

33 Extracts of hop cones, the female flowers of *Humulus lupulus* L., are used for adding aroma
34 and flavor in the beer-brewing process. Hops contain hundreds of components but of
35 particular interest are the so-called resins, containing mainly hop acids, hop oil, and
36 polyphenols. These three classes of resin are important as biochemical markers to differentiate
37 hop varieties. The hop acids, part of the soft resin fraction, consist of two related series, the
38 α -acids (humulone, cohumulone, and adhumulone) and the β -acids (lupulone, colupulone, and
39 adlupulone) (1). Besides the two series of normal-, co-, and ad-homologues there are also
40 some minor hop acids in the plant, including posthumulone/postlupulone,
41 prehumulone/prelupulone and adprehumulone (2). These are present as a complex mixture of
42 varying composition and concentrations. The relative proportions of α -acids and β -acids as
43 well as the content of co-homologues depend on the hop variety and, for any given variety, on
44 the growing conditions. Many different varieties of the *H. lupulus* L. species exist, each one
45 with its own different composition and agronomic characteristics. Traditionally, hop varieties
46 have been classified into two groups, namely, “aroma” or “bitter” types, depending on their
47 α -acid content and flavor characteristics.

48 Hops are prone to oxidation and chemical deterioration. Both the α - and β -acids are very
49 susceptible to oxidation and degradation during storage. Their oxidation products affect beer
50 flavor significantly because once α -acids have been oxidized, they can no longer be
51 isomerized into iso- α -acids; thus, the hops’ bittering potential decreases, and the aroma
52 becomes unpleasant and “cheesy”. It is also important to package the hops properly, which
53 involves keeping them in refrigerated storage at temperatures of between 0 and 5 °C,
54 removing as much oxygen as possible, and storing them in an oxygen barrier material (3, 4).
55 Apart from the storage conditions, each variety has a particular tendency to be oxidized, and
56 so the oxidation state of hops is an important quality factor that needs to be looked at closely
57 for quality control in the brewing industry.

58 During the brewing process the virtually insoluble α -acids of the hop extract are converted
59 into the more soluble iso- α -acids, which give the typical bitter taste to the beer. In addition to
60 imparting bitter taste, iso- α -acids exhibit other interesting features: they have tensioactive
61 properties, thereby stabilizing the beer foam, and they inhibit the growth of Gram-positive
62 bacteria. An analysis of the hop acids in hops is important for quality control, and many
63 methods have been developed to provide a quantitative analysis of the α -acids in hops and
64 hop products. A widely used empirical method extracts the bitter components into solvents

65 and measures them quantitatively by spectrophotometry. HPLC with UV detection is also
66 routinely used to analyze bitter acids (5-12). Nevertheless, UV is neither sensitive nor
67 selective enough for the direct identification of minor hop acids in complex mixtures. The
68 instability and structural similarity of the bitter hop acids cause difficulty in routine analysis.
69 Recently, the detection of these compounds by HPLC coupled to mass spectrometry was
70 investigated. The six major bitter hop acids have been analyzed by HPLC coupled with
71 atmospheric pressure ionization tandem mass spectrometry (APCI-MS-MS) (2) and with
72 negative electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (13). Other techniques such as capillary
73 electrophoresis (CE) in its different modes have been applied to the analysis of hop acids, that
74 is, capillary zone electrophoresis (CZE) (14), micellar electrokinetic chromatography
75 (MEKC) (15, 16), and microemulsion electrokinetic chromatography (MEEKC) (17-19),
76 using a UV detector. The iso- α -acids have also been determined using MEKC-UV (20-23).
77 The aim of this work has been to develop the first fast and simple capillary
78 electrophoresis-electrospray ionization mass spectrometry (CE-ESI-MS) method for the
79 identification of hop acids and their oxidation compounds in four varieties of hops: Saaz,
80 Nugget, Magnum, and Columbus. We have also determined iso- α -acids in beer to
81 demonstrate the applicability of this method.

82

83 MATERIALS AND METHODS

84 **Chemicals.** The hop acid standard, an international calibration extract ICE 2, composed of a
85 mixture of α -acids (34.94% humulone + adhumulone and 14.45% cohumulone) and β -acids
86 (12.02% lupulone + adlupulone and 12.92% colupulone), and the iso- α -acid standard ICS-I2,
87 with a mixture of 64.3% *trans*-iso-R-acids (iso-humulone, isoadhumulone, and
88 iso-cohumulone) were from Labor Veritas, Zürich, Switzerland.

89 Ammonium acetate, ammonium carbonate, acetic acid, and diethylamine were from Panreac
90 (Barcelona, Spain), ethanolamine and diethanolamine were from Aldrich (Steinheim,
91 Germany), and ammonia was from Merck (Darmstadt, Germany), all of which were used for
92 the CE running buffers at different concentrations and pH values. Buffers were prepared by
93 weighing the quantity indicated in doubly distilled water and adding 2 M ammonium
94 hydroxide to adjust the pH. Triethylamine (TEA) was from Aldrich, and HPLC grade
95 2-propanol used in the sheath flow, acetone, and sodium hydroxide were from Panreac. All
96 solutions were filtered through 0.45 μ m Millipore (Bedford, MA) membrane filters before
97 being injected into the capillary. Distilled water was deionized using a Milli-Q system

98 (Millipore). DSC-Diol and DSC-C18 solid-phase separation (SPE) cartridges were from
99 Supelco (Bellefonte, PA).

100

101 **Instrumentation.** For CE separations we used a P/ACE System MDQ (Beckman
102 Instruments, Fullerton, CA) equipped with a UV-visible detector and a 0-30 kV high-voltage
103 built-in power supply. A bare fused-silica capillary with 50 μm i.d. was from Composite
104 Metal Services (Worcester, U.K.). The detection length to the UV detector was 7 cm, and the
105 total length was 100 cm (corresponding to the MS detection length). The instrument was
106 controlled by a PC running System 32 Karat software from Beckman.

107 CE was coupled using an electrospray interface (ESI) (model G1607A from Agilent
108 Technologies, Palo Alto, CA) to the MS detector (Bruker Daltonics, Squire 2000). A
109 commercial coaxial sheath-flow interface was used (vide infra). The coaxial sheath liquid and
110 the electrical contact at the electrospray needle tip were delivered by a 74900-00-05 Cole
111 Palmer syringe pump (Vernon Hills, IL). An ESI-MS interface provided both a coaxial sheath
112 liquid makeup flow and a nebulization gas to assist droplet formation. Both the drying gas and
113 the nebulization gas were nitrogen. The mass spectrometer was used in the negative-ion
114 mode, and the capillary voltage was set at 4000 V. The ion trap scanned within the m/z
115 300-700 range at 13000 u/s during separation and detection in the scan mode. The maximum
116 accumulation time for the ion trap was set at 5.00 ms, the target count was set at 20000, and
117 the trap drive level was set at 100%. For the connection between the CE system and the
118 electrospray ion source of the mass spectrometer the outlet of the separation capillary was
119 fitted into the electrospray needle of the ion source, and a flow of conductive sheath liquid
120 made electrical contact between the capillary effluent and water for the electrospray needle.
121 The instrument was controlled by a PC running Esquire NT software from Bruker Daltonics.
122 Before the first use, the uncoated capillaries were conditioned using a rinse with 0.1 M NaOH
123 for 10 min followed by a rinse with water for 5 min and finally a rinse with running buffer for
124 30 min. Capillary conditioning between runs was carried out by flushing the column for 3 min
125 with water and finally for 5 min with the separation buffer. At the end of the day the capillary
126 was rinsed with water for 30 min and dried for 10 min.

127

128 **Hop Samples and Beer.** Hop pellets of the varieties Saaz and Nugget and bottles of “extra”
129 beer were obtained from the company Grupo Cervezas Alhambra S.L. (Granada, Spain),
130 whereas the varieties Columbus and Magnum were provided by S.A. Española de Fomento
131 del Lúpulo (León, Spain).

132 It is known that drying temperatures >65 °C cause variable losses of hop acids (3), so we
133 induced the oxidation of the α - and β -acid standards and four hop varieties: Saaz, Nugget,
134 Columbus, and Magnum. The hop pellets were received in intact, lightproof packaging. Ten
135 grams was reduced to powder with a mortar and heated for 2h at 80 °C in an oven. We also
136 studied the natural oxidation of Saaz and Nugget by keeping pellets of the harvest of the year
137 2000 in a plastic vessel at room temperature and in the presence of light for 2 years.

138

139 **Extraction of Hop Acids and Oxidized Derivatives of the Hop Pellets.** To recover the hop
140 acids present in the pellets and their oxidized derivatives, we studied different organic
141 solvents (methanol, ethanol, and acetone) with water (0:100, 25:75, 50:50, 75:25, and 100:0).
142 The extraction protocol was as follows: 2.5 g of hop pellets, previously reduced to powder
143 with a mortar, was extracted three times with 50 mL of acetone/water (75:25 v/v) for 10 min
144 each time. The extracts were combined and brought to dryness in a rotary evaporator under
145 reduced pressure at 60 °C to get rid of any residual solvent. During the last step, 2 mL of
146 acetone/water (50:50 v/v) was added to dissolve the extract, which was then passed through a
147 0.20 μ m membrane filter and analyzed by CE-ESI-MS.

148 The extraction protocol of the naturally oxidized derivatives and the compounds obtained by
149 induced oxidation was the same for both methods and for all four varieties of hops studied.

150

151 **Extraction of Isomerized Hop Acids in “Extra” Beer.** We assayed two different cartridges,
152 DSC-Diol and DSC-C18, and obtained the best results with DSC-C18. Thus, the subsequent
153 extraction protocol of isomerized hop acids was as follows: a DSC-C18 cartridge placed in a
154 vacuum elution apparatus was conditioned by passing 20 mL of acetone/water (75:25 v/v) and
155 then 10 mL of water through it. Subsequently, 100 mL of degassed “extra” beer was passed
156 through the column. The isomerized hop acids were recovered by passing four portions of 5
157 mL of acetone/water (75:25 v/v). The final volume was dried in a rotary evaporator under
158 reduced pressure at 60 °C. The residue was reconstituted in 2 mL of acetone/water (50:50 v/v)
159 and passed through a 0.20 μ m filter before CE-ESI-MS analysis.

160

161 **General Procedure.** The optimum conditions used for the CE-ESIMS separation method
162 were as follows: running buffer, 160 mM ammonium carbonate/ammonium hydroxide; pH 9;
163 voltage, 20 kV; 7 s injection time; sheath liquid, 2-propanol/water, 50:50 v/v, with 0.1% TEA
164 delivered at a flow rate of 3 μ L/min; drying gas flow rate, 4 L/min at 150 °C; nebulizing gas
165 pressure, 6 psi; and MS analyses carried out using a compound stability of 25%.

166 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

167 **Development of the CE-ESI-MS Method.** The effects of different separation parameters
168 were studied to obtain the best selectivity, sensitivity, and resolution conditions. The
169 CE-ESI-MS method was optimized using the extract obtained with 75:25 v/v acetone/water
170 from oxidized Saaz hops because this extract was the most complex and its electropherogram
171 presented the greatest number of peaks. First, the optimum concentration and pH of four
172 volatile running buffers, ammonium carbonate/ammonium hydroxide, diethylamine/am-
173 monium hydroxide, ammonium hydroxide/acetic acid, and ammonium acetate/ammonium
174 hydroxide, were established. The pH of ammonium carbonate/ammonium hydroxide was
175 assayed between 8.5 and 10 at a concentration of 100 mM, and pH 9 showed the best
176 resolution. The concentration was then studied between 100 and 190 mM at pH 9, the best
177 resolution being found with 160 mM.

178 After studying the influence of pH between 9.5 and 10.5 at a concentration of 100 mM, we
179 chose pH 10.5 as optimum. Diethylamine/ammonium hydroxide was assayed in the range
180 between 100 and 500 mM, and the best resolution was found to occur at a concentration of
181 500 mM. The pH and concentration using ammonium hydroxide/acetic acid as running buffer
182 were also examined. The effect of pH was studied by using a concentration of 500 mM of
183 ammonium hydroxide and adjusting the pH with acetic acid to between 9 and 10. We chose
184 pH 9.5 as the optimum value, and the concentration was then assayed between 100 and 500
185 mM at this pH. Higher concentrations were tried, but these produced noises in the baseline.

186 The pH of ammonium acetate/ammonium hydroxide was assayed by varying it between 8 and
187 11 when using a concentration of 160 mM. The greatest number of peaks appeared at pH
188 10.5. We then studied the concentration effect between 80 and 180 mM and found the best
189 result with a concentration of 160 mM. **Figure 1** shows the optimum electropherograms
190 found in the different studies carried out with the four running buffers under optimum
191 conditions. Of all of the conditions studied, ammonium carbonate/ammonium hydroxide at
192 pH 9 at a concentration of 160 mM offered the most information about the compounds of
193 interest.

194 To obtain better resolution between peaks, different percentages (5, 10, and 15%) of organic
195 solvents such as 2-propanol and sodium dodecyl sulfate (SDS) at 5 and 10 mM were added to
196 the buffer without success. The voltage was varied between 10 and 30 kV, and finally a
197 voltage of 20 kV was selected to obtain the best resolution. The injections were made at the
198 anodic end using N₂ pressure of 0.5 psi for 7 s (1psi=6894.76 Pa). These conditions were
199 chosen for the optimization of the ESI parameters.

200 It is well-known that the choice of sheath liquid has significant effects on sensitivity and on
201 the electrical contact between CE and ESI (24, 25). Generally, a small amount of volatile
202 TEA is used for ESI-negative detection (26). Next, the sheath liquid composition and flow
203 rate were optimized to increase the MS sensitivity of the compounds. Different sheath liquids
204 were tested, that is, methanol/water and 2-propanol/water at different proportions, with 0.1%
205 TEA and without TEA. With 2-propanol as organic solvent we obtained a better response than
206 with methanol. Eight different percentages of sheath flow liquid were tested:
207 2-propanol/water at 40:60 v/v, 50:50 v/v, 60:40 v/v, and 70:30 v/v, with and without 0.1% v/v
208 TEA in order to facilitate electrical contact when the negative mode was used. A 50:50 ratio
209 of propanol/water with 0.1% v/v TEA as sheath liquid was judged to obtain the highest signal
210 and best current stability. The choice of these variables represented a compromise between
211 maintaining efficient electrophoretic separation and improving ionization performance. The
212 influence of the sheath liquid flow rates of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$ was also examined. We
213 observed that the best results in terms of MS sensitivity were obtained when using a flow rate
214 of 3 $\mu\text{L}/\text{min}$. The nebulizer pressure was then optimized by testing values of 2, 4, 6, 8, and 10
215 psi, the greatest sensitivity being obtained with 6 psi. The temperature of the interface was
216 also optimized between 100 and 300 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, the greatest sensitivity being obtained at 150 $^{\circ}\text{C}$.
217 Another important parameter of the interface was the stability of the compound, which was
218 studied between 25 and 100%. The MS signal decreased concomitantly with higher
219 percentages because the number of molecules transferred into MS was low, whereas with
220 lower percentages the majority of the compounds became more stable, as indicated by an
221 increase in the MS signal. This parameter is related to the voltage used in the capillary placed
222 at the MS entrance; thus, the higher this parameter, the higher the voltage applied by the MS
223 instrument and therefore the higher the solute fragmentation that can take place at that point.
224 Thus, we chose 25% compound stability.

225 **Figure 2** shows the base peak electropherogram and the extracted ion electropherogram
226 obtained under the CE-ESI-MS conditions chosen for an extract of oxidized Saaz hops.
227 Fifteen different compounds can be recognized: m/z 377.3 corresponds to
228 humulinone/adhumulinone (overlap), oxidation products of humulone/adhumulone. Oxidation
229 occurs leading to the creation of a double acyloin entity. The acyloin rearrangement with
230 concurrent ring contraction may take place at both C-4 and C-6. This reaction is totally
231 analogous to the important isomerization reaction of humulone to the isohumulones (**Figure**
232 **3a**); an ion with a ratio m/z of 393.3 indicates that two oxygen atoms have been incorporated
233 into humulone/adhumulone (overlap). This oxidation product belongs to the

234 abeo-isohumulone group, which is derived from isohumulones but obtained directly through
235 the oxidation of humulone. It is very likely that humulinone represents the first step in the
236 reaction sequence. These oxidized compounds have a five-membered structure. The reaction
237 mechanism of these compounds (**Figure 3b**) proceeds via the oxidation of the
238 3-methyl-2-butenyl side chains in humulinone, followed by cyclization, via either
239 intramolecular dehydration or nucleophilic cleavage of the intermediate oxirane ring (*I*). The
240 ions with m/z ratios of 409.2 and 425.2 are thought to be more highly oxidized compounds,
241 thus indicating that three and four oxygen atoms, respectively, have been incorporated into
242 humulone/adhumulone, but their structure and the formation mechanism are still unknown;
243 m/z 363.3 corresponds to cohumulinone, an oxidation product of cohumulone, with a structure
244 and oxidation mechanism similar to that of humulinone, and the m/z of 379.2 could be due to
245 the incorporation of two oxygen atoms into cohumulone, in the same way as with humulone;
246 m/z 331.2, hulupone/adhulupone (overlap), and m/z 317.2, cohulupone, correspond to the
247 oxidation of the t-acids lupulone/ adlupulone and colupulone. The structures of the oxidation
248 products indicate that the lengths of the side chains in these compounds, together with the
249 double bonds and hydroxyl groups, easily give rise to oxidation cyclizations, leading to five
250 derivatives (**Figure 3c**) (m/z 375.2, prehumulone). Other compounds have been found in this
251 extract: m/z 341.1, maltose; m/z 577.2, procyanidin; m/z 609.2, hesperedin (18.6 min) and
252 rutin (19.5 min); m/z 447.1, luteolin-7-*O*-glucoside (17.2 min) and kaempferol-3-*O*-glucoside
253 (20.5 min); m/z 463.1, quercetin-4'-*O*-glucoside; and m/z 337.1, desmethylxanthohumol. Some
254 of them have easily been identified and confirmed using the hop acid standard.
255 The reproducibility of the CE-ESI-MS analysis, expressed by the relative standard deviation
256 (RSD) of six consecutive injections, was 3.6% for the retention time and 6.9% for the peak
257 area, both quite suitable for the intentions of this work.

258

259 **Analysis of Acids in Different Hop Varieties.** To demonstrate the capacity of the
260 CE-ESI-MS method for the analysis of this type of compound in hop samples, we applied the
261 method to different varieties. Four varieties were studied: Saaz (a classic variety with good
262 aroma but poor storage stability); Nugget and Magnum (with similar properties of high
263 α -acid, acceptable aroma, and good storage stability); and Columbus (with high α -acid, a
264 strong but pleasant aroma, but poor storage stability).

265 **Table 1** shows information about the structures of the compounds found in the four varieties
266 of hop with no oxidation. As can be seen in this table, m/z 377.3, which corresponds to
267 humulinone/adhumulinone, appears in all varieties. Humulinone is perhaps the best known
268 nonvolatile oxidation product derived from humulone. Nugget hop is the variety with the best
269 result because it contains fewer oxidized compounds, only cohumulinone (m/z 363.2),
270 humulinone/adhumulinone (m/z 377.3), and another oxidation product of humulone with m/z
271 409.3. Columbus is the variety with the poorest storage stability, and so it contains more
272 oxidized compounds; in addition to some of the components present in Nugget we also found
273 cohulupone (m/z 317.2) and hulupone/adhulupone (m/z 331.2). These oxidation derivatives
274 also appear in the varieties Saaz and Magnum, although the oxidation compound of
275 cohumulone (m/z 363.2) does not appear in these varieties.

276 **Analysis of Oxidation Derivatives in Different Varieties of Hops.** The oxidation of hops
277 was forced by heating 10 g to 80 °C for 2 h. We also studied two varieties, Nugget and Saaz,
278 oxidized at room temperature for about 2 years. **Table 2** shows information about the
279 structures of the compounds found in the four varieties of hops subjected to forced oxidation.
280 The presence of characteristic hop compounds such as humulone/ adhumulone (m/z 361.2)
281 can be seen in the varieties Nugget, Magnum, and Columbus together with cohumulone (m/z
282 347.3) and lupulone/adlupulone (m/z 413.2). Colupulone (m/z 399.3) is to be found in only
283 Nugget and Magnum. Apart from this, the typical oxidized compounds of α -acids
284 [humulinone/ adhumulinone (m/z 377.3) and cohumulinone (m/z 363.2)] and β -acids
285 [hulupone/adhulupone (m/z 331.2) and cohulupone (m/z 317.2)] were to be found in all of the
286 varieties. It can also be seen that the majority of α - and β -acids disappeared when we forced
287 the oxidation in Saaz. Colupulone disappeared in Columbus. Other oxidation products have
288 been found (m/z 379.2, 393.3, 409.2, 425.2, and 427.2), but they are not shown in the table.
289 For naturally oxidized Saaz and Nugget hops, only oxidation compounds appear, except for
290 cohumulone, due to oxidation being more extensive over a longer period of time (**Table 3**).

291 **Figure 4** shows the differences between samples of Saaz hops. We found that in the Saaz
292 hops subjected to both forced and natural oxidation the maximum peak was at 393.3,
293 corresponding to the gain of two oxygens into humulone. **Figure 5** shows the differences
294 among hop Nugget without oxidation, hop Nugget with forced oxidation, and naturally
295 oxidized hop Nugget. The same applied to the Nugget variety where both oxidized forms
296 showed a maximum peak at 393.3.

297 **Figure 6** shows the electropherogram of the samples of hop Magnum: hop Magnum without

298 oxidation and hop Magnum with forced oxidation. With the Magnum variety we can detect
299 the presence of peaks with m/z ratios of 361.2, corresponding to humulone/adhumulone,
300 399.3, corresponding to colupulone, and 413.3, corresponding to lupulone/adlupulone in both
301 oxidized and nonoxidized hops.

302 **Figure 7** shows the electropherogram of the samples of hop Columbus: hop Columbus
303 without oxidation and hop Columbus with forced oxidation. In this variety, the most
304 characteristic oxidation compounds found in Columbus are humulinone/ adhumulinone (m/z
305 377.3) and cohumulinone (m/z 363.3).

306 Comparing the results for the four samples, we can deduce that the Saaz variety contains
307 fewer hop acids than the other varieties. Nugget samples with no oxidation show the least
308 number of oxidized derivatives, and thus this variety has the best storage stability. Magnum
309 has the highest α - and β -acid contents.

310

311 **Determination of Iso- α -acids in “Extra” Beer.** Iso- α -acids, hop-derived compounds present
312 in low concentrations in beers, are primary flavor constituents. The bitterness of beer is
313 largely attributable to iso- α -acids, which are formed by isomerization during the wort-boiling
314 stage of beer production (3). The identification and quantification of iso- α -acids in an “extra”
315 beer was carried out using the CE-ESI-MS method proposed, after preconcentrating 100 mL
316 of the beer sample using a DSC-C18 column. The sample was recovered by passing it through
317 four portions of 5 mL of acetone/water (75:25 v/v). The extract was dried, reconstituted in 2
318 mL of acetone/water (50:50 v/v), and filtered before analysis. The recovery percentage was
319 ~70% for the iso- α -acids using this extraction system. **Figure 8a** shows the electropherogram
320 of a mixture of three iso- α -acid standards, **Figure 8b** the mass spectra of isohumulone and
321 iso-adhumulone, which have an m/z ratio of 361.2, and **Figure 8c** the mass spectra of
322 iso-cohumulone, which has an m/z ratio of 347.2. **Figure 9** shows the electropherogram and
323 the mass spectra of an “extra” beer. As can be seen in this figure an unknown peak appears at
324 m/z 329.2, and the iso- α -acids appear at m/z 361.2 and 347.2.

325 The quantification was carried out using calibration graphs studied between 25 and 500 mg
326 L^{-1} . The correlation coefficients (r^2) obtained for the regression lines of the CZE plots of peak
327 area versus concentration were all >0.998. Detection limits for the analytes were 2.00 mg L^{-1}
328 for isohumulone + iso-adhumulone and 2.22 mg L^{-1} for isocohumulone, and the limits of
329 quantification were 6.67 mg L^{-1} for iso-humulone + iso-adhumulone and 7.41 mg L^{-1} for iso-

330 cohumulone, all of which were calculated by the IUPAC (27). The precision of the method
331 was evaluated by determining the repeatability of the peak areas. The repeatability values
332 obtained for three successive injections of a standard solution of 300 mg L⁻¹ for each analyte
333 were ~5.7%.

334 The concentration found for isohumulone + iso-adhumulone was 2.26 mg L⁻¹ and that for
335 iso-cohumulone, 1.05 mg L⁻¹, in the initial beer sample, which was with Saaz hops. This
336 variety is characterized by its high aroma and its low α-acid content, which in turn implies a
337 low iso-α-acid content.

338

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CAPTION FIGURES

Figure 1. Comparison between different running buffers: (a) ammonium carbonate/ammonium hydroxide, 160 mM at pH 9; (b) diethylamine/ammonium hydroxide, 500 mM at pH 10.5; (c) ammonium hydroxide/acetic acid, 500 mM at pH 9.5; (d) ammonium acetate/ammonium hydroxide, 160 mM at pH 10.5. Experimental conditions: 50 μ m i.d. fused-silica capillary, 100 cm detector and total length, 20 kV, 7 s of hydrodynamic injection at 0.5 psi; sheath liquid, 2-propanol/water, 50:50 v/v, containing 0.1% TEA; flow rate, 3 μ L/min; dry gas, 4 L/min, 150 $^{\circ}$ C; nebulizing gas pressure, 6 psi. MS analyses were carried out using negative polarity. Compound stability was 25% MS scan m/z 300–700 (target mass m/z 550). Sample was oxidized hop pellets of the variety Saaz.

Figure 2. Base peak electropherogram and extracted ion electropherogram. Conditions: buffer ammonium carbonate/ammonium hydroxide, 160 mM at pH 9; 50 μ m i.d. fused-silica capillary, 100 cm detector and total length, 20 kV, 7 s of hydrodynamic injection at 0.5 psi; sheath liquid, 2-propanol/water, 50:50 v/v, containing 0.1% TEA; flow rate, 3 μ L/min; dry gas, 4 L/min, 150 $^{\circ}$ C; nebulizing gas pressure, 6 psi. MS analyses were carried out using negative polarity. Compound stability was 25%

Figure 3. (a) Conversion of humulone into humulinone; (b) oxidation mechanism for the formation of the compound with molecular weight (M) 394 from humulinone; (c) conversion of lupulone into hulupone.

Figure 4. Differences among samples of Saaz hops: (a) without oxidation; (b) with forced oxidation; (c) naturally oxidized. The separation conditions are shown in Figure 2

Figure 5. Differences among samples of Nugget hops: (a) without oxidation; (b) with forced oxidation; (c) naturally oxidized. The separation conditions are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 6. Differences among samples of Magnum hops: (a) without oxidation; (b) with forced oxidation. The separation conditions are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 7. Differences among samples of Columbus hops: (a) without oxidation; (b) with forced oxidation. The separation conditions are shown in **Figure 2**.

Figure 8. (a) Electropherogram of a mixture of three trans iso- α -acid standards: 1, trans-iso-humulone and trans-iso-adhumulone; 2, iso-cohumulone. (b) Mass spectra of isohumulone and iso-adhumulone with a m/z ratio of 361.2. (c) Mass spectra of iso-cohumulone with a m/z ratio of 347.2.

Table 1. Structures of compounds found in different varieties of hops without oxidation.

analyte	[M-H] ^a			
	Saaz	Nugget	Magnum	Columbus
posthumulone				303.5
cohulupone	317.2		317.2	317.2
hulupone/adhulupone	331.2		331.2	331.2
cohumulone	347.3	347.3	347.3	347.3
humulone/adhumulone	361.2	361.2	361.2	361.2
cohumulinone		363.2		363.2
prehumulone	375.2		375.2	
humulinone/adhumulinone	377.3	377.3	377.3	377.3
colupulone	399.3	399.3	399.3	399.3
lupulone/adlupulone	413.3	413.3	413.3	413.3

^a[M-H] is the deprotonated ion.

Table 2. Structures of compounds found in different varieties of hops with forced oxidation

analyte	[M-H] ^a			
	Saaz	Nugget	Magnum	Columbus
posthumulone				
cohulupone	317.2	317.2	317.2	317.2
hulupone/adhulupone	331.2	331.2	331.2	331.2
cohumulone		347.3	347.3	347.3
humulone/adhumulone		361.2	361.2	361.2
cohumulinone	363.2	363.2	363.2	363.2
prehumulone	375.2		375.2	
humulinone/adhumulinone	377.3	377.3	377.3	377.3
colupulone		399.3	399.3	
lupulone/adlupulone		413.2	413.2	413.2

^a[M-H] is the deprotonated ion.

Table 3. Structures of compounds found in naturally oxidized Saaz and Nugget hops

analyte	[M-H] ^a	
	Saaz	Nugget
posthumulone		
cohulupone	317.2	317.2
hulupone/adhulupone	331.2	331.2
cohumulone	347.3	347.3
humulone/adhumulone		
cohumulinone	363.2	363.2
prehumulone		
humulinone/adhumulinone	377.3	377.3
colupulone		
lupulone/adlupulone		

^a[M-H] is the deprotonated ion.

Figure 1.

Figure 2.

Figure 3.

Figure 4.

Figure 5.

Figure 6.

Figure 7.

Figure 8.

